

DEPENDENCE OF THE OPTICAL ROTATION OF QUININE SALTS ON THE CHARGE OF THE QUININE IONS

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Studies have been made on the variations of the molecular rotations of quinine salts with temperature, concentration and additions of various electrolytes. The rotation increases with dilution and decreases with temperature. The addition of acids to quinine hydrochloride increases its rotation and a maximum value is reached for the addition of 1.47 mols. of hydrochloric acid to each mol. of the quinine salt. Chlorine ions have an inhibiting effect on the rotation of quinine salts and so also have certain other electrolytes which may be placed in the order : HCl , NaCl , MgCl_2 , AlCl_3 , NaNO_3 , $(\text{COOH})_2$, Na_2SO_4 , H_3PO_4 , Na -acetate ($+\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$) $>$ H_2SO_4 $>$ citric acid.

The observations can generally be explained by assuming that the variations are due to variations of the charge on the quinine ions. A quantitative interpretation of the increase of rotatory power of quinine hydrochloride on the addition of hydrochloric acid has been offered on this basis.

The characteristic optical rotatory powers of cinchona alkaloids provide a potentially valuable means for their assay and test of purity, but the sensitiveness of the rotations to various influences often adversely affects the precision of the methods. Since the classical work of Oudemans (*J. Pharm. chim.*, 1884, *v*, 9, 338), who described a method for the polarimetric estimation of cinchonidine in quinine tartrate, a number of investigators have attempted to develop methods of assay of quinine based on optical rotation. But except for P. Helvetica V and French Codex, 1937, which have adopted optical rotation for limit tests of other alkaloids in quinine, the polarimetric method has not yet come into general usage as a recognised method of assay of quinine alkaloids.

The influence of acids on the rotations of quinine has received considerable attention. Hesse (*Annalen*, 1873, 166, 217) first observed that the optical rotation of a quinine salt increased with the addition of acid and a maximum was reached when the amount of acid added sufficed to convert the basic salt into the normal salt. Liquier (*Compt. rend.*, 1926, 183, 195; *Ann. Physique*, 1927, *x*, 8, 121) found that the curves connecting $[\alpha]$ with p_H showed two flat portions corresponding with basic and normal sulphates. Andrews and Webb (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, 13, 232) on the other hand failed to confirm the presence of such plateaux in the curve of optical activity corresponding to the two salts. Lapp (*Compt. rend.*, 1933, 196, 970; *Anal. Chim. Appl.*, 1933, 18, 289) claimed to have observed two inflexions in the $[\alpha]$ — p_H curves of quinine, one at p_H 4.6 to 6.5 and the other at less than 2.0, corresponding with the basic and neutral salts and suggested a method of the polarimetric estimation of quinine at p_H 5.5. The concentrations of acid in the quinine solution for assay by the optical method, as recommended by different authorities, however, show wide variations and so also the concentrations of quinine and the ratios of acid to quinine present in the solution. This will be apparent from Table I.

TABLE I

Authority.	Quinine salt used	Acid added.	Conc. of quinine.	Conc. of acid added.	Rotation		Temp.
					$[\alpha]_D$.	$[M]_D$.	
1. Oudemans (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	Tartrate (dihydrate)	HCl	0.07435M	0.300N	-221.5°	-882.0°	17°
2. Koppeschaar (<i>Pharm. J.</i> , 1885, <i>iii</i> , 18, 809)	Tartrate (anhydrous)	HCl	0.0328	0.120	-230.0°	-877.8°	15°
3. French Pharmacopoeia, 1908	Sulphate (anhydrous)	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0268	0.0816	-243.5°	-908.3°	15°
4. Allen's Commercial Organic Analysis, Vol. VII, 5th Ed., p. 470	Tartrate, sulphate or hydrochloride	HCl	0.0513	0.225	-272.9° (Q base)	-884.2°	17°
5. French Codex, 1937 (Extra Pharmacopoeia, Martindale, Vol. II, 22nd Ed., 1943, p. 143)	Sulphate (anhydrous)	H ₂ SO ₄	0.0670	0.0125	-240°	-895.2°	?
6. Thorpe's Dictionary of Applied Chemistry, Vol III, 4th Ed., p. 133	Tartrate (monohydrate)	HCl	0.0613	0.250	-272.9° (Q base)	-884.2°	17°
7. Henry, Plant Alkaloids, 3rd Ed., 1939, p. 399	Sulphate (anhydrous)	H ₂ SO ₄	0.025	0.100	-247.1	-921.7°	15°
8. Andrews & Webb (<i>loc. cit.</i>)	Sulphate (anhydrous)	Nil	0.0077	Nil	-176° (Q base)	-570.3°	25°
9. Do	Bihydrochloride	Nil	0.0077	Nil	-270°	-874.8°	25°

Obviously, if the optical rotation is to be used as a method of assay, standard conditions for the procedure should be established on a rational basis. This would require a study of the various factors on which the rotation depends. Emde (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1932, **15**, 557) concluded from his observations that the asymmetric C₉-atom in the quinine molecule is responsible for a numerically larger amount of rotation than the other three asymmetric carbon atoms put together and that the increase of rotation from the monohydrochloride to the bihydrochloride should be attributed to this C₉-atom. Again, according to Dietzel and Söllner (*Arch. Pharm.*, 1930, **268**, 629) the increase of rotation of quinine hydrochloride on the addition of acid is due to the ionisation of the quinoline-nitrogen atom. Since the rotation of a dyssymmetric molecule is altered by variations in the dipole forces in the molecule (cf. Kauzmann, Walter and Nyring, *Chem. Rev.*, 1940, **26**, 339), the introduction of a free charge, as by ionisation, should have a marked effect on the rotation. Further, the latter would be influenced by all factors which might cause a variation of this charge. Hydrogen ions would be expected to have a predominant effect on the ionisation of quinine, but the interaction of quinine ions with other ions, by virtue of either chemical or electrical forces, should also modify the effective charge. The ionisation should depend on the concentration and temperature of the solution as well. That such influences do alter the rotation of quinine salts is borne out by the present investigation, details of which are embodied in this paper.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Standard Quinine Solution.—Quinine sulphate and hydrochloride of B.P. quality, as available in the market, were recrystallised twice from water and dried at 100°. For preparing quinine tartrate, the purified hydrochloride was dissolved in water, and a solution of pure sodium potassium tartrate was added to the boiling solution, which was cooled with continuous stirring. The precipitate of quinine tartrate was recrystallised from water, and finally dried at 100°, i.e., to the monohydrate stage. These salts were used for preparing the standard solutions.

Polarimetric Measurements.—A polarimeter by Franz, Smidt and Haenz, reading to 0.01°, in conjunction with an electric sodium lamp was used for the measurements. All readings were taken in a 2 dcm. tube. At least 3 readings were taken for each measurement and the mean was taken for calculation of the rotatory power.

The rotatory powers have been expressed in the various tables in terms of both the specific rotation and the molecular rotation, the relationship being

$$[M] = \frac{[\alpha] \times \text{mol. wt.}}{100}$$

For quinine sulphate, which contains two molecules of quinine base, half of the molecular weight was taken for calculation in order to get all the results in terms of the quinine molecule.

Variations of the Optical Rotatory Power of Quinine Salts with additions of Different Electrolytes

Quinine Tartrate.—The salt was dissolved in water with the addition of the minimum quantity of hydrochloric acid to yield a stock solution which was 0.3127*M* with

TABLE II

Optical rotation of quinine tartrate with additions of electrolytes.

Conc. of quinine.	Electrolyte added.	Conc. of electrolyte in solution.	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$	$[M]_D^{20}$	Change of rotation due to addition of electrolyte (%).
0.03127 <i>M</i>	None	Nil	-200.2°	-799.0°	...
0.02502	HCl	1.86 <i>N</i>	-182.7°	-729.0°	-8.76 (decrease)
"	NaCl	1.71	{ -179.7° -178.2°	{ -717.0° -711.0°	{ -10.26 -11.01
"	NaNO ₃	1.18	-190.5°	-760.0°	-4.87
"	{ Na ₂ SO ₄ { H ₂ SO ₄	0.70 0.10	-195.4°	-779.6°	-4.43
"	{ Na ₂ HPO ₄ { HCl	2.11 0.51	-196.9°	-785.6°	-1.68
"	H ₃ PO ₄	4.01	-197.8°	-789.2°	-1.22
"	CH ₃ COOH (glacial)	1.75	-210.9°	-841.5°	+5.32 (increase)

respect to quinine and contained 0.048*N*-hydrochloric acid. The electrolyte was added to 16 c.c. of the solution and the volume in each case was made up to 20 c.c. with water, so that the final concentration of quinine in each case was 0.02502*M*. The results are shown in Table II.

Quinine Sulphate—Quinine sulphate was dissolved in water with the addition of minimum quantity of sulphuric acid. To this stock solution were added electrolytes and water to make up the volume in such proportions that the final solution was in each case 0.0268*M* with respect to quinine and, in most cases, 2.0*N* with respect to the added electrolyte. Besides, the final solution contained 0.0505*N*-sulphuric acid corresponding to the amount added for making the stock solution. The results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

Optical rotation of quinine sulphate with added electrolytes.

Quinine=0.0268*M*. H₂SO₄ (originally present)=0.0505*N*.

No.	Electrolyte added.	Conc. of added electrolyte.	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$.	$[M]_D^{20}$.	Change of rotation due to electrolyte (%).
1.	None		-223.5°	-833.6°	**
	H ₂ SO ₄ (<i>N</i> /10) added for dilution	0.0984 <i>N</i>			
2.	H ₂ SO ₄	2.0	-219.0°	-816.9°	- 2.03
3.	Na ₂ SO ₄ H ₂ SO ₄ added for keeping in soln.	2.0 } 0.2025 }	-215.0°	-802.0°	- 3.79
4.	Na ₂ SO ₄ HCl added for keeping in soln.	2.0 } 0.0521 }	-214.5°	-800.1°	- 4.02
5.	HCl	2.0	-197.5°	-736.7°	-11.62
6.	NaCl	2.0	-199.5°	-744.1°	-10.74
7.	NaNO ₃	2.0	-211.0°	-787.0°	- 5.59
8.	CH ₃ COONa H ₂ SO ₄ added for keeping in soln.	2.0 } 1.53 }	-218.0°	-813.1°	- 2.46
9.	Acetic acid	2.0	-230.0°	-857.9°	+2.55 (increase)
10.	Oxalic acid	2.0	-212.0°	-790.8°	- 5.13
11.	Citric acid	2.0	-219.5°	-818.7°	- 1.79
12.	H ₃ PO ₄	2.0	-216.5°	-807.5°	- 3.13
13.	MgCl ₂	2.0	-199.0°	-742.3°	-10.95
14.	AlCl ₃	2.0	-208.5°	-777.7°	- 6.71

Another series of measurements was taken with the same quinine sulphate solution and under identical conditions, but with the addition of varying quantities of sodium chloride. The results are shown in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Conc. of quinine = 0.0268M.

Conc. of NaCl	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$.	$[M]_D^{20}$.	Change of rotation due to NaCl (%).
0	-223.5°	-833.6°	...
0.0214N	-224.5°	-837.4°	+ 0.45
0.214	-218.0°	-813.1°	- 2.46
0.428	-215.0°	-802.0°	- 3.79
0.856	-209.5°	-781.4°	- 6.26
2 000	-199.5°	-744.1°	-10 74

TABLE V

Optical rotation of quinine hydrochloride with additions of acids.

Conc. of quinine = 0.0322M.

Conc. of acid.	Mol. of acid per equiv. of base.	p_H .	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$.	$[M]_D^{20}$.	Change of rotation due to acid (%).	α .	$[M]_{calc}$.
1. Nil	1.0	5.86	-151.2°	-545.1°		0	-545.1°
2. 0.00526N-HCl	1.1634	5.45	-167.1°	-602.5°	+10.53	0.1635	-598.7°
3. 0.01052	1.3268	4.95	-182.2°	-656.8°	+20.49	0.3280	-652.6°
4. 0.01578	1.4902	4.55	-199.4°	-734.5°	+32.91	0.4888	-705.2°
5. 0.02104	1.6536	4.25	-212.3°	-765.5°	+40.43	0.6509	-758.3°
6. 0.02630	1.8170	3.95	-225.2°	-812.1°	+49.17	0.8110	-810.8°
7. 0.03156	1.9804	3.70	-236.0°	-850.6°	+56.04	0.9530	-857.3°
8. 0.03682	2.1438	3.42	-240.3°	-866.5°	+58.98		
9. 0.04734	2.4706	2.85	-243.0°	-872.7°	+60.10		
					Diff. from maximum value.		
10. 0.1053	4.268	1.75	-237.7°	-857.1°	- 1.79		
11. 0.1579	5.907	1.58	-233.9°	-843.2°	- 3.38		
12. 0.2752	9.547	Not detd.	-232.6°	-838.5°	- 3.92		
13. 1.2384	39.46	„	-217.5°	-784.2°	-10.24		
14. 1.9500	61.56	„	-208.4°	-751.5°	-13.89		
					Diff. from orig. rotation.		
15. 0.03156N-H ₂ SO ₄	1.9804	„	-236.4°	-852.5°	+56.40		
16. 0.04734	2.4706	„	-241.2°	-870.0°	+59.60		

Quinine Hydrochloride.— Varying quantities of standard hydrochloric acid and sulphuric acid solutions were added to a given volume of a solution of quinine hydrochloride in water, keeping the final volume constant in each case by the addition of water. The final concentration of quinine was in each case 0.0322M. The variations of the p_H values and of the optical rotations are given in Table V.

A similar study was made of the influence of varying concentrations of sodium chloride on the optical rotation of quinine hydrochloride, with or without the previous addition of hydrochloric acid in proportion sufficient to raise the rotation to the maximum value. The results are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

Optical rotation of quinine hydrochloride with addition of HCl and/or NaCl.
Conc. of quinine = 0.0322M.

No.	Concentration.		[Cl ⁻]	[α] _D ²⁰ .	[M] _D ²⁰ .	Change of rotation due to electrolyte (%).
	HCl.	NaCl.				
1.	Nil	Nil	0.0322N	-151.2°	-545.1°	...
2.	"	0.0577N	0.0899	-150.7°	-543.5°	-0.29
3.	"	0.2885	0.3207	-149.9°	-540.4°	-0.86
4.	"	0.5770	0.6092	-147.6°	-535.7°	-1.72
5.	"	1.2384	1.2706	-143.5°	-518.6°	-4.86
						Diff. from maximum value.
6.	0.0511N	0.0577	0.1410	-238.6°	-860.2°	- 1.43
7.	0.0511	1.1870	1.2713	-217.5°	-784.2°	-10.14

Variations of Optical Rotation of Quinine Salts with Temperature

The rotation of a 0.06805M solution of quinine tartrate containing 0.24N- sulphuric acid was determined at temperatures 25°, 30° and 35°. Similar measurements were made with a 0.053M solution of quinine sulphate in 0.0969 N-sulphuric acid at temperatures 30.6°, 37.4° and 51.2°, and in this case the refractive indices of the solutions were also determined at the corresponding temperatures using a Zeiss dipping refractometer. The results are shown in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Variations of optical rotation of quinine salts with temperature

Temp.	[α] _D .	[M] _D .	Ref. index.	$\left(\frac{n^2+2}{3}\right)^2$	$\left(\frac{n^2+2}{3}\right)^3$
Quinine tartrate (0.06805 M)					
25°	-216.2°	-862.6°	...	...	...
30°	-209.4°	-835.5°	...	...	...
35°	-201.3°	-803.2°	...	...	...
Quinine sulphate (0.0969 M)					
30.6°	-221.9°	-827.7°	1.33700	1.59396	-519.3
37.4°	-218.1°	-813.5°	1.33602	1.59172	-511.1
51.2°	-211.8°	-790.0°	1.33372	1.58659	-498.0

Variations of the Optical Rotation with Concentration of Quinine Salts

A few measurements were taken for studying the effect of concentration on the optical rotations of quinine tartrate and hydrochloride solutions. The results are shown in Table VIII.

TABLE VIII

Optical rotations of quinine salts at varying concentrations.

No.	Particulars.	Conc of quinine	$[\alpha]_D^{20}$.	$[M]_D^{20}$.
1.	Quinine tartrate (in 0.48N-HCl)	0.31270M	-191.1°	-762.5
2.	Do diluted 10 times	0.03127	-201.0°	-802.1
3.	Quinine tartrate (in 0.24N-H ₂ SO ₄)	0.06805	-209.4°	-835.5°
4.	Do diluted with equal volume of water	0.03402	-214.7°	-856.7°
5.	Quinine hydrochloride (in aq. soln.)	0.06120	-148.7°	-536.0°
6.	Do 10 c.c. diluted to 19 c.c. with water	0.03220	-151.2°	-545.1°

DISCUSSION

The results recorded above show that the molecular rotations of different quinine salts at similar concentrations are not identical, though the variations are not large. The following order has been noticed:

$Q.HCl$ (in excess HCl) $>$ $Q_2.H_2SO_4$ (in excess H₂SO₄) $>$ Q tartrate (in excess HCl) $>$ $Q.HCl$ (aqueous solution).

It seems that caution is necessary in accepting the sweeping generalisations sometimes made, e.g., that all quinine salts, containing an equivalent amount of alkaloid, give the same rotation when dissolved in the same large excess of hydrochloric acid (Allen's Commercial Organic Analysis, Vol. VII, 5th Ed., p. 470).

FIG. 1

Among the electrolytes studied, acids have the greatest effect on the optical rotation of quinine. Curve 1 in Fig. 1 shows that the rotation of quinine hydrochloride increases almost linearly with additions of hydrochloric acid till about 0.9 equivalent of acid has been added to one molecule of quinine. The curve bends subsequently and a maximum rotation is reached for the addition of 1.47 equivalents of acid. This observation is in consonance with those of Dietzel and Söllner (*loc. cit.*) but is at variance with the statements often made that the maximum rotation corresponds with the formation of the bihydrochloride of quinine, *i.e.*, with the addition of one equivalent of acid per molecule of quinine (cf. Thorpe's Dictionary of Applied Chemistry, 4th Ed., Vol. III, p. 149; Liquier, *loc. cit.*).

An exactly similar increase of rotation of the quinine hydrochloride solution takes place on the addition of sulphuric acid in place of hydrochloric acid, at the corresponding concentrations (vide Table V). This indicates that the effect is due to hydrogen ions of the acid.

Fig. 2, curve 1 shows that after the maximum rotation of the quinine hydrochloride solution has been reached, further addition of hydrochloric acid causes a gradual decrease of the rotation and that this decrease from the maximum value amounts to about 14% as the concentration of the acid approaches 2.0 N (vide Table V). If again after sufficient hydrochloric acid has been added to the quinine hydrochloride for attaining the maximum rotation, sodium chloride is added instead of hydrochloric acid, the rotation is decreased to exactly the same extents as with the additions of corresponding equivalent quantities of the acid (vide Table VI, also Fig. 2). This shows that the decrease of rotation is in both cases due to the increase of chlorine-ion concentration. [The decrease of rotation due to the addition of excess hydrochloric acid was noticed by Hesse (*loc. cit.*)

FIG. 2

Curves 1—4 refer respectively to $Q.HCl+HCl$; $Q_2.H_2SO_4+NaCl$; $Q.tartrate+NaCl$, $Q.HCl+NaCl$; + sign refers to $Q.HCl+0.0511N-HCl+NaCl$

but no further reference to any investigation of this point was found in the literature].

That chlorine ions have a depressing effect on the rotations of other quinine salts as well is shown by curves 2, 3 and 4 in Fig. 2, corresponding to quinine sulphate, tartrate and hydrochloride respectively (cf. also Tables II, III, IV and VI). With quinine sulphate (Table III), the addition of hydrochloric acid, sodium chloride and magnesium chloride had nearly the same effect at 2*N* concentration, but the lowering of rotation caused by aluminium chloride was appreciably smaller. It appears that the cation has little effect on the rotation and the smaller effect of the aluminium salt is presumably due to a lower activity of the chlorine ions in aluminium chloride solution.

Tables II and III show the effect of several other electrolytes on the rotations of quinine tartrate and sulphate respectively. It will be seen that although most of the electrolytes added have a lowering effect on the rotation in a greater or less degree, chlorides have by far the maximum effect. These may be arranged in the following order: HCl, NaCl, MgCl₂ > AlCl₃ > NaNO₃ > (COOH)₂ > Na₂SO₄ > H₃PO₄ > Na-acetate (+ H₂SO₄) > H₂SO₄ > citric acid.

The observations indicate that the effects are probably due to the anions, but the above order does not strictly correspond to the order of valency, though the monovalent chlorine and nitrate ions show the largest effect and the tribasic citric acid, the minimum effect. Acetic acid provides an exception by increasing the rotations of both the quinine salts studied, but sodium acetate causes a small decrease. This point deserves further investigation.

Since the electrolytic ions probably exert their influence on the rotation of quinine salts, the rotatory power of quinine would also appear to depend on the ionic form in which it is present. Quinine being a diacidic base may exist in solution in the following forms: Q, QH⁺ and QH₂⁺⁺. QH⁺ should be present mainly in the hydrochloride solution and QH₂⁺⁺ in the bishydrochloride, and so a difference in the optical rotatory powers of the two ionic forms would qualitatively explain the nature of the variations observed on the addition of acid to the hydrochloride. Hypotheses on such basis have previously been postulated by Liquier (*loc. cit.*), Lapp (*loc. cit.*) and by Dietzel and Söllner (*loc. cit.*).

A quantitative examination of the question would involve the calculation of the proportions of the two types of ions at various stages during the addition of acid to quinine hydrochloride. In a mixture of quinine hydrochloride and hydrochloric acid, the following equilibrium may be assumed to exist:

The values of the dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 of the QH₂⁺⁺ ion are 4.3×10^{-11} and 2×10^{-11} respectively (Pedersen, *Dansk. Tids. Farm.*, 1934, 8, 17). On account of the large difference between the values of the two dissociation constants, the second stage of dissociation, i. e., the concentration of the uncharged Q molecules, may be

neglected in an acidic solution, as obtains during the addition of acid to quinine hydrochloride. The equation for electroneutrality in such a solution may be written as :

$$\frac{[\text{QH}_2^{++}]}{Cx} + \frac{[\text{QH}^+]}{C(1-x)} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{(C_1 - Cx)} = \frac{[\text{Cl}^-]}{(C + C_1)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where C is the molar concentration of quinine, C_1 , the concentration of added hydrochloric acid and x is the fraction of the quinine molecules present in the QH_2^{++} form. Therefore,

$$K_1 = \frac{[\text{QH}^+][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{QH}_2^{++}]} = \frac{C(1-x)(C_1 - Cx)}{Cx}, \text{ whence,}$$

$$Cx^2 - x(C + C_1 + K_1) + C_1 = 0 \quad \dots (3)$$

The values of x calculated from the quadratic equation (3) with different values of C_1 , are given in column 8 of Table V.

If we now assume the value -545.1° for the molecular rotation of quinine hydrochloride as due to QH^+ ions alone, and the maximum value -872.7° as due solely to QH_2^{++} ions, the molecular rotation of a solution containing a mixture of the two ionic forms will be given by

$$[M]_{\text{calc.}} = -(545.1^\circ + 327.6 x) \quad \dots (4)$$

The values of $[M]_{\text{calc.}}$ calculated from equation (4) are given in the last column of Table V. Curve 2 in Fig. 1 was obtained by plotting the above values, but the last three points represent the values of $[M]_{\text{calc.}}$ corresponding to those of C_1 calculated from equation (3) by substituting respectively the values 0.985, 0.99 and 0.995 for x . The close correspondence between the observed and calculated curves tends to justify the assumptions on which the calculations were made.

Since the optical rotatory power of quinine shows increase with the charge of the quinine ions, factors which would alter the charge would be expected to alter the rotation also. When chlorine ions are added in excess to quinine hydrochloride in acid solution having the maximum rotation, an association of the oppositely charged ions, QH_2^{++} and Cl^- to form a complex of the type QH_2Cl^+ might be considered as taking place. This would reduce the effective charge of the quinine ion, and therefore the rotation, as observed in curves 1, 2 and 3 in Fig. 2. The slopes of the descending portions of these three curves are almost identical, tending to indicate that the same type of interaction is taking place in these cases.

Curve 4 in Fig. 2 for quinine hydrochloride and sodium chloride shows a slower decrease of rotation with increase of chlorine ions. Here, an ion-association of the type

may be postulated, but the attractive force would be weaker than that between QH_2^{++} and Cl^- , which would explain the smaller depression of the optical rotation.

Similarly, the effect of other electrolytes in reducing the optical rotation of quinine salts may be attributed to the interaction between the quinine cations and the anions of the electrolytes to form ion-complexes of reduced charge. A regular variation of the effect with the valency of the added anion would be expected in such cases, but the observed absence of such regularity, the characteristically prominent effect of chlorine ions and the anomalous behaviour of acetic acid point to some sort of specificity in these interactions.

Table VIII shows that a decrease of the concentration of quinine salts results in an increase of the molecular rotation. This would appear to be due to the dissociation of the salt molecules into the respective ions resulting in an increase of the ionic forms which produce higher rotations.

The rotation of quinine salts is found to decrease with increase of temperature (vide Table VII and Fig. 3). Increase of temperature may bring about, among others, the following types of changes in the solution of the quinine salt :—

- (1) Decrease of density resulting in a decrease of the refractive index.
- (2) Increase of the freedom of rotation within the molecules, thus reducing the asymmetry (e.g., about the axis joining the C_2 and C_3 carbon atoms).

FIG. 3

According to Guye and Aston (*Compt. rend.*, 1897, 124, 194; also cf. Walden, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 363), optical rotation generally decreases with increasing temperature, but

the magnitude of the decrease is usually rather small and probably results from decrease in refractive index due to decrease in density. This conclusion would, however, apply to molecules already possessing freedom of rotation. The following relations have been found to hold between the refractive index, n , and molecular rotation (Kauzmann, Walter and Eyring, *loc. cit.*).

$$[M]_D \div \left(\frac{n^2 + 2}{3} \right) = \text{Constant} \quad (5)$$

$$[M]_D \div \left(\frac{n^2 + 2}{3} \right)^2 = \text{Constant} \quad (6)$$

Equation (6) is said to have given better constancy in certain cases. The values of $[M] / \left(\frac{n^2 + 2}{3} \right)^2$, calculated for quinine sulphate, have been given in the last column of Table VII and also plotted in curve 3, Fig. 3.

Comparison of the curves 2 and 3 in Fig. 3 shows that although the slope of the change is reduced by correcting the molecular rotation for refractive index in the above manner, actual constancy is not thereby attained. This would indicate that other factors also come into play including the increase of freedom of rotation of the molecule about the axis connecting the asymmetric carbon atoms C_8 and C_9 .

Further work on the standardisation of conditions for the assay of quinine by optical rotation is in progress.

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